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SEROPREVALENCE OF ANTI-*Borrelia* ANTIBODIES IN PATIENTS WITH 2ND AND 3RD DEGREE A-V BLOCK

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Introduction: *Borrelia burgdorferi sensu lato* (Bb s.l.) complex consists of different types of spirochetes, of which some are pathogenic for humans. Patients with symptomatic Lyme carditis most often present in an acute form varying degrees of occasional A-V blocks as a consequence of conduction system disorders of the heart. Here we wanted to examine frequency of exposure to Bb s.l. in patients with A-V block of 2nd and 3rd degree by detection of anti-*Borrelia* antibodies.

Materials and methods: Serum samples were acquired from patients reported to Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases of Vojvodina with A-V block of 2nd and 3rd degree and forwarded to Pasteur Institute Novi Sad for quantification of anti-*Borrelia* IgG. Paired serum sample from each patient is collected four weeks later. Anti-*Borrelia* IgG were quantified via ELISA using highly specific recomWell *Borrelia* IgG assay, while Immunoblot recomLine *Borrelia* IgG and IgM was used as 2nd tier assay. Finally, serological findings were combined with basic demographic data provided by the patient (gender, residency and age).

Results: From total of 30 patients enrolled in the study (n = 30), majority were males (20/30; 66.66%). Average age of patients was 69.9 years (95% CI 65.5 - 74.4 years), while municipalities of Novi Sad and Bečej were most reported as place of residence (11/30; 36.66% and 4/30; 13.33%, respectively). Anti-*Borrelia* IgG were found in serum samples 85-year old male from Bečej (73 IU/ml and 71 IU/ml; cut-off: 24IU/ml). Immunoblot analysis showed presence of anti-VlsE IgM and IgG in patient serum sample, without specific anti-OspC antibodies that could reveal *Borrelia* genospecies responsible for their synthesis.

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Conclusions: Seroprevalence of anti-*Borrelia* antibodies in patients with A-V block of 2nd and 3rd degree is 3.33%. Given that current sample size is not sufficient for drawing of generalised conclusion, examination of anti-*Borrelia* antibodies in patients with A-V block should be continued.

Keywords: *Borrelia*, A-V block, Lyme, Lyme carditis